

Why Alexander the Great should have accepted Darius III's offer of half the Persian Empire

by Brian Paul Kaess

In this paper, I will explore the reasons why Alexander the Great turned down the offer by Darius III, after the Battle of Issus (333 BCE), to accept literally half the Kingdom of Persia, in exchange for peace, and to further argue that this was indicative of a trend in Alexander towards excessive 'hubris' that was to foreshadow his own eventual downfall and lead to the ruin of not only himself, but his descendants, wives, and other family members as well, in something we might call 'the Curse of Alexander.' For Alexander, in literally trying to conquer the known world at the time, had violated that most ancient of Delphic maxims, 'Nothing to excess¹,' and in rejecting Darius III quite generous terms, literally hastened his own ruin and merely sped more quickly towards his own eventual demise.

For although winning victory after victory in far, distant Asia, Alexander perhaps succeeded, in the long term, in merely degrading his own forces to the point where his once robust force was merely a ragtag semblance of itself. And this may have proven a hazard to him where he was in much need of close compatriots on his return trip, where some suspect he may have been poisoned. Alexander's continuous pursuit of his own ambitions in Asia may have 'poisoned the well' and literally given opportunity to those less zealous followers a chance to plot against him.

Also, there were two sides to Alexander: 1) a generous, merciful and compassionate side (especially towards women)- reflective of moderation- in which Alexander will forever remain beloved and where he glowed, and 2) an angry, wanton, spiteful side (often driven by elongated drinking bouts) of his personality in which he committed some of his most regretful, tragic, and short-sided acts. These latter draconian acts by Alexander cast judgement on his character, even for one who had been educated at the hands of Aristotle. Another excessive trend in Alexander is that he lived in a world where achieving greatness and glory in martial combat and achieving great ends often competed with the practical needs of staying alive and keeping an army intact. He not only pushed his men, but *drove* them. In fact, he drove them so much to the furthest reaches of Asia, that many often wondered when they would return and even complained to Alexander that it was time to turn back to the land of Hellas and Macedon. It is little wonder that many felt beleaguered and weary.

Just as in Xenophon's *Anabasis*², so too Alexander's men had found themselves 'strangers in a strange land', in hostile terrain, and many leagues distant from home. And many would perish before ever seeing the sight of Macedon again, including Alexander himself. This is the great irony of Alexander: he achieved great things, but at what cost to himself and those closest to him. It is sad but true that Alexander's own ambition may have been pivotal in leading to his eventual downfall.

¹ See 'Delphic maxims' [Wikipedia.org](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delphic_maxims)

² See 'Anabasis (Xenophon)' [Wikipedia.org](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Anabasis_(Xenophon))

Now let us look at Alexander's beginnings before diving into some of the events and battles that led up to his decisions when he came vis-à-vis with Darius III's offer of sharing the Persian kingdom. We will also look at some of Alexander's tactics that made him one of the leading generals in olden times. So let us treat here of Alexander's life in a compass of a brief narrative.

In antiquity, there was Plato of Ariston and Aristotle of Stagira, and so too there was Alexander III of Macedon (356 BCE-323 BCE), known to the wider world as Alexander the Great³. Alexander's birth was preceded by a number of portents.⁴ Born in Pella on July 6th⁵, the son of King Philip II and Olympias (his 4th wife), Alexander was groomed for greatness from an early age, being tutored by none other than Aristotle himself in the Temple of the Nymphs. He became regent and heir apparent at age 16 and began his military career versus the Thracians to the north. After his father Philip II was assassinated in 336 BCE, Alexander was proclaimed king on the spot.

After securing his northern borders in the Balkan campaign and destroying Thebes and subduing Athens, Alexander consolidated his Greek allies with the League of Corinth⁶ (or Hellenic League) in order to unify Greek military forces under Macedonian leadership, where Macedon was clearly 'first among equals.' Alexander's plan to conquer Persia had originally been hatched by his father and, after his death, Alexander took up this idea with zeal. It was no doubt to be considered a 'payback' to the Persians for their previous invasions of Greece under Darius I and Xerxes and to put the Persian menace to rest once and for all. For no one would threaten Greece & Macedon who had been 'put under the heel.'

They would eventually cross into Asia and pass 365 stades, for it is said they wanted to make the number of stades⁷ their army traveled the same as the number of days in the year⁸. However, Alexander's army traveled about 1,500 miles upon reaching their furthest extent at the Hyphasis river in South Asia, before turning back. This includes the march through Bactria, the Hindu Kush, the Indus Valley, and into the Punjab region. This was about 13,000 stades.

³ Alexander the Great *Wikipedia.org*

⁴ Quintus Curtius Rufus, *History of Alexander* bk I p. 4.

⁵ This was apparently the same day that the Temple of Diana burned. See Plutarch *Alexander*. New York, Phillips & Hunt, p. 1.

⁶ League of Corinth *Wikipedia.org*

⁷ A stade in Greek terms would be roughly 185 meters, so 365 stades would be akin to 67.5 kilometers or about 42 miles.

⁸ Diodorus Siculus, *Bibliotheca historica* II, 7, 3-5, p. 199.

Here is a short list of some of the most significant battles during Alexander's campaigns into Asia Minor, the Levant, Assyria & Babylonia, Persia, and so forth:

1. Battle of the Granicus (334 BCE) – His first major victory in Asia Minor, where he defeated a coalition of Persian satraps and opened the gateway into Anatolia.
2. Siege of Halicarnassus (334 BCE) – A tough coastal siege in Caria, where Alexander overcame strong Persian and Greek resistance to secure southwestern Asia Minor.
3. Battle of Issus⁹ (333 BCE) – A pivotal clash in modern-day southern Turkey where Alexander defeated Darius III for the first time, capturing his family and sending shockwaves through the Persian Empire.
4. Siege of Tyre (332 BCE) – A legendary seven-month siege of the island city in the Levant. Alexander built a causeway to breach the city's defenses, securing control of the eastern Mediterranean. The aid of a naval force from Cyprus helped turn the tide and was key to the victory.
5. Siege of Gaza (332 BCE) – A brutal and symbolic victory that opened the road to Egypt. The city's fall demonstrated Alexander's resolve and strategic patience.
6. Battle of Gaugamela (331 BCE) – Often considered his greatest triumph, this battle in Assyria (modern Iraq) saw Alexander decisively defeat Darius III and effectively end Achaemenid rule. The hesitation and faltering of the Persian cavalry (i.e. their failure to exploit) might have cost Darius III the victory, and put him on the run.
7. Battle of the Persian Gate (330 BCE) – A fierce mountain pass battle in Persia, where Alexander outflanked a last-ditch Persian defense and cleared the path to Persepolis.
8. The Siege of the Sogdian Rock in early 327 BCE in modern-day Tajikistan, also known as the Rock of Ariamazes, where Alexander used a psychological ploy to achieve a surrender. One of the captured prisoners struck Alexander so much with her beauty that she became his wife.

Alexander, especially in the arts of war, was renowned for his usual *gravitas*, a man of 'high adventure' but high seriousness as well. He was known not only for his sweeping, flanking cavalry charges, but even his 'decapitation' strikes at the enemy rear, which could quickly cause an enemy host to flounder and break. He would use them in his famous hammer-and-anvil tactics, using the Macedonian phalanx and their bristling wall of spears (called *sarissas*) and forward pressure to immobilize the enemy or 'hold them in place' while the elite Companion Cavalry would strike the enemy's side or rear (i.e. 'the hammer'). What Ney was to Napoleon, so too Alexander was to

⁹ Alexander's Campaign- Alexander's Persian Campaign at Alexander-the-great.org

his men- ‘not just a hero, but a talisman.’ Just like Ney, you get the feeling all Alexander had to do was to give you an order for you to feel brave¹⁰.

Moreover, who could forget the image of Darius III fleeing in abject terror before the semblance of Alexander at the Battle of Issus (333 BCE) as shown on the Alexander Mosaic¹¹ in Pompeii? There was also his keenness and persistence during sieges such as that of Tyre, when he stayed the course until the final storming of the island. He showed adroitness in decision-making when he outflanked his enemy at the Battle of the Persian Gate (330 BCE), overcoming an initial disaster of boulders being thrown upon his men from heights above. This flanking movement may be similar to Lee at Chancellorsville (1863), for Alexander had used a local shepherd to flank the defenders and not only gain the victory but obtain half the Persian empire at little expense. Little wonder why Alexander’s legend constantly grew and there seemed to be no shortage of those who wished to follow him- including past adversaries.

It should also be known that Alexander wasn’t a one-man show and was adept at inspiring loyalty in his subordinates and gathering around himself capable and invigorating leaders in their own right. To list a few: Hephaestion¹² (his closest friend), Parmenion¹³, Perdiccas¹⁴, Craterus, Seleucus, Ptolemy Lagus¹⁵, Antigonus & Cleitus the Black (who held overall command of his Companion Cavalry or *Hetairoi*). His most able cavalry commander was Cleitus the Black, who saved Alexander’s life at the Battle of the Granicus (334 BCE), by cutting down a Persian noble who was about to strike Alexander from behind.

Now let us address the main point of this paper. After the Battle of Issus (333 BCE), Darius III sought to save a portion of his kingdom by negotiating with Alexander and offered generous terms on a number of occasions, the most famous being the 2nd round of negotiations. His offer to Alexander was, according to ancient sources such as Arrian¹⁶, Curtius Rufus, and Diodorus Siculus, as follows:

1. All territory west of the Euphrates River (essentially half of the Persian Empire),
2. 30,000 talents of silver as ransom for his captured family,
3. Marriage alliance—offering his daughter, Stateira II, to Alexander.
4. And in some versions, co-rulership of the Achaemenid Empire.

¹⁰ The Lion’s Last Roar: Marshal Michel Ney *historynet.com*

¹¹ The Alexander Mosaic is currently housed in the National Archeological Museum, Naples in Naples, Italy.

¹² Arrian, *Anabasis of Alexander* I.II.6-12, p. 51.

¹³ Quintus Curtius Rufus, *History of Alexander* bk II p. 35.

¹⁴ Arrian, *Anabasis of Alexander* I.14.1-5, p. 61.

¹⁵ Diodorus Siculus, *Bibliotheca historica* 1.25.26, p. 61.

¹⁶ ‘Battle of Guagamela’ *worldhistory.org*

Darius III was eager to repatriate his own family- mother, wife and daughters, who Alexander had captured after Issus. He no doubt noticed that they had been treated well for prisoners, and this was no doubt a result of Alexander's prejudice favoring royalty and women better than normal common soldiers. He himself had grown up with royal intentions and this was no doubt that was the lens in which he viewed the world. There is little doubt that Alexander had a sense of chivalry on certain occasions, although one can say there were two sides to Alexander's coin. He could at once be generous and kind to those who surrendered and at other times cruel and almost vicious. Darius III was trying to play to his better self when he made his famous offer. Yet, Alexander declined, saying there could never be two suns - it would upset the world order¹⁷. Not even the Persian Immortals would save Darius.

This unbridled and unchecked ambition was most unfortunate, in the long run, I would argue, not only for Alexander but for his own descendants, who would suffer greatly under the *Diadochi* or successors. The result was that there were not two suns (Persian and Greek) or one sun (Alexander), but, after a generation, a state of affairs in which Alexander's family members were wiped off the face of the earth- literally *no* sun at all! Alexander was a man of sublime ambition. Yet he was certainly a victim of his own goal and dream to conquer Asia.

Also, Alexander must have viewed Darius' offer as a sign of weakness and not seen it as the opportunity it was. A chance for peace, co-rule and a more successful chance at Persianization which, in any case, he later sought to adopt- even after his victory at Guagamela. Even his own general Parmenion thought the offer held a fair chance of success, when he stated: "If I were Alexander, I would accept what was offered and make a treaty." But Alexander replied: "So would I, if I were Parmenion." Alexander had chastised him before when he had said bluntly: "I too should prefer money to glory, if I were Parmenion¹⁸."

Another problem for Alexander was his increasing Persianization as the campaign continued. He began wearing Persian dress, adopted court rituals like *proskynesis* (prostration), and surrounded himself with Persian courtiers. Macedonian soldiers had fought to conquer Persia, not to see their king emulate it, and they must have been offended. Macedonian soldiers were free-minded folk and could barely imagine bowing before their king. There was a sense that Alexander was drifting away from his roots¹⁹.

The Romans were no fan of Alexander in this regard either. Pliny, in his *Naturalis Historia*, criticizes Alexander for introducing Eastern luxuries to the West. For instance, he mentions Alexander's use of perfumes and rare gems, and his lavish banquets, as examples of decadence that later Romans emulated. Such hedonism would seem harmless to us today, but may have seemed out of place for 'an army on the march'

¹⁷ 'Battle of Guagamela' worldhistory.org

¹⁸ Quintus Curtius Rufus' *History of Alexander* bk IV, p. 268.

¹⁹ 'Alexander and the Iranians' A. B. Bosworth *The Journal of Hellenic Studies* Vol. 100, Centenary Issue (1980), pp. 1-21.

eager to return home to Macedon and Hellas. His enlightened fusion was viewed as nothing more than bordering on apostasy.

Alexander perhaps made up for these shortcomings to his men with the Susa weddings in 324 BCE, in which eighty of his Macedonian nobleman married Persian noblewomen, a chance to bind the two kingdoms through intermarriage, not merely conquest. He himself married Stateira II, daughter of Darius III, and Parysatis, daughter of Artaxerxes III. His closest companion, Hephaestion, married Stateira's sister, Drypetis, making them brothers-in-law. There was no doubt he wanted to unify his empire and secure loyalty from both sides. So, perhaps, for a brief moment, before his suspected poisoning in 323 BCE, Alexander had had the last laugh. And just imagine if Alexander had lived longer- his Persianization might have been a roaring success.

Alexander's 1st and most beloved wife was Roxana ('little star' or 'bright one'), of Bactrian origin, who he fell in love with at first sight²⁰. She accompanied him on his campaigns, including India. At the time of Alexander's death in 323 BCE, she was pregnant, and gave birth to Alexander IV, who was declared co-king alongside Alexander IV's half-brother Philip III Arrhidaeus. To secure her son's claim to the throne, Roxana allegedly murdered Alexander's other wives, including Stateira II and Parysatis, daughters of Persian royalty.

A period of *interregnum* strife had begun. Initially protected by Olympias, Alexander's mother, they fell into the hands of Cassander when he had her assassinated in 316 BCE and then he followed suit by ending Roxana and Alexander IV's lives in 310 BCE in secret. So once a trusted son of Macedonia, Cassander emerged to be the most ruthless of all the *Diadochi*, thus bringing to a close the Argead dynasty.

It is here we see that Alexander's decision not to accept Darius III's offer of a divided kingdom displayed arrogance on his part and caused Alexander to 'work a little harder', 'go a little further', 'sweat a little more' for the glory he so desired. By accepting Darius III's offer, he could've realized a certain glory close at hand, and perhaps not alienated so many of those he had 'dragged along' to the furthest corners of Asia. Knowing no bounds to his ambitions, Alexander was a case study in extremes, and this perhaps was the most important factor leading to his own downfall as well as that of those closest and most beloved to him. 'The Curse of Alexander' which saw fate strike down Alexander at a young age and those closest to him who had conquered much of Asia, was to be the hallmark of the *Diadochi* and a testament to the view that glory itself is fleeting.

²⁰ 'Alexander the Great Spouse: Roxana and the Two Other Wives' *ancient-literature.com*